

Article: Critical Discourse Analysis: A Comparative Study of the Semiotic and Textual Features of Health Cards

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Critical Discourse Analysis: A Comparative Study of the Semiotic and Textual Features of Health Cards

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ABSTRACT

The government of a country is responsible for providing better healthcare facilities to its people. The political parties claim to facilitate the people and healthcare facilities are an important part of it. In Pakistan, two of the political parties namely Pakistan Tehreek e Insaaf (PTI) and Pakistan Muslim League Noon (PMLN) during their governments-initiated healthcare programs and issued health cards for deserving people. The current research has analyzed the textual and visual features of these cards and has conducted a comparative study. Cards carry some symbolic features in them as the political ideologies of the said parties are implicitly depicted in the cards. This research deals with the visual and linguistic analysis of the cards. The research focused on the functions of these cards related to national and political ideologies and how both cards are similar or different from each other. The study has done a comparative analysis using a visual analysis¹ approach and textual analysis using Norman Fairclough's three-dimensional model. The results of this analysis are stated in textual and visual analysis.

Keywords: visual analysis, semiotic features, critical discourse analysis, political ideology, health cards.

Introduction

Communication is the source of delivering our ideas to others and the mode of communication saw a dramatic change in recent decades. Now communication is not limited to only verbal expressions. It has been extended to include other non-verbal forms such as visual imagery, signs, symbols, colours, sculptures, gestures, and other semiotic resources.² One major reason for this change in the mode of communication is the phenomenon of globalization and the digitalization of the world³. It has a greater impact on how people use

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verbal and non-verbal aspects of communication to persuade people to agree with them. It is a fact that verbal and non-verbal language is inseparable. Therefore, communication includes multimodal features in multiple contexts. The producers of the text exploit different semiotic resources to project their messages in the discourse. Further, according to research, “in human history, the visual image has never been more dominant than it is now.”⁴

In today’s world of digitalization, visuality and imagery in communication have an important place that leads toward the scholarship of visual analysis. The researchers were of the view that the inclusion of visual analysis can go back to the “late 1980s and 1990s when several authors who had been working in linguistics began to realize that meaning is generally communicated not only through language but also through other semiotic modes.”⁵ The scholars who stress the importance of visual analysis argue that images are subject to interpretation in the same way as words are to be analyzed through linguistic theories. Based on this assumption, Kress opines that visual information is richer and has broader potential both pragmatically and semantically than verbal because the interplay between semiotic elements creates more powerful meanings.⁶ It also strengthens the fact that multimodality in political discourse contributes to diversity in its rhetorical meanings because visual ingredients aesthetically affect the viewers.

The inclusion of visuals in political discourse has become a vital aspect because visuals convey the themes and ideologies of political parties impressively. It draws the attention of the people and delivers relevant political information. The interaction and employment of semiotic resources and other visual modes in political discourse make it attractive and persuasive to the readers.⁷ The expression of thoughts and ideas is not limited to verbal communication in any context such as politics, advertisement, branding, and the like. Body language, gestures, images, focus, and colours also contribute to making communication meaningful. Each unit of non-verbal communication is significant for enforcing the message. In the current paper, our focus will be on multimodality in the political context.⁸

Imagery and visuality are important aspects of political expression. In politics, there is a trend for using visual resources to gain fame and popularity. Politicians make their slogans, claims, and achievements popular among people by using both linguistic and semiotic resources. Likewise, visuality is used as a media strategy to represent or construct the achievements of politicians or political parties, their good actions, or initiatives they take for

public welfare. Visualization in the political text is employed as a tool to arouse deeper feelings in the viewers. Therefore, it is generally assumed that visuality can better agitate the audience to persuade for a certain action than verbal or textual elements.⁹ Political parties always publicize their good initiatives even if it is a matter of public interest. They want to own the credit for their actions to ensure the popularity of their political visions. Both health cards underpin the same ideology; therefore, it will be our focus of analysis.

Literature Review

The analysis of visual and graphic elements in political communication has recently gained much importance. The researchers¹⁰ studied the visualization of political communication using a multimodal approach in the texts employed in political campaigns. His study explored how textual and visual modes are used in political campaigns to establish important political information. He analyzed textual, verbal, still, and motion visuals. His findings concluded that political discourse in campaigns is persuasive because of the verbal and visual interaction with other musical modes. The other researchers¹¹ presented a similar study on the discourse analysis of images and visuals in a political rally in Southwest Nigeria by using a multimodal approach. They used Halliday's systemic functional linguistics as a framework for the analysis of the text. His findings revealed that the projection of party colours in the visual images implied the political ideologies and the wearing of those colours by the party supporters suggested their political commitment and loyalty. The study concluded that semiotic resources have an important part to play in the wide range of success of political rallies because they reveal socio-cultural and political codes.

A group of researchers¹² carried out a multimodal analysis of the advertisement of an online marketplace, Shopee. This research considered both verbal and visual features of this advertising discourse. The study examined verbal components by using Halliday's language Metafunction theory¹³ and visual aspects by using Kress & Leeuwen's multimodal framework.¹⁴ Their findings gave the conclusion that along with verbal features, visuals and images are instrumental in attracting the attention of the consumers to buy goods and services offered by the online store analyzed the WHO banner regarding the precautionary measure to avoid the Covid-19.¹² He adopted a multimodal approach in his study to analyze the verbal and visual aspects to identify the underlined objective of the banner. By using a qualitative descriptive approach, they analyzed the data by adopting the Kress and Leeuwan

model for visual analysis. This research showed that visuals and graphics are more helpful for building relations with the public to persuade them. Further, the target people give more attention to the meaning that is encoded in the semiotics.

The above-given literature review underlines the employment of visual elements in political discourse in general. However, it is worth mentioning here that descriptive analyses of multimodal texts are also accomplished with an object to serve some political purposes. Similarly, the two researchers¹⁵ conducted a multimodal analysis of political cartoons published in two of the Pakistani newspapers. They took twelve cartoons equally from both newspapers and carried out a comparative analysis showing the different attitudes of the newspaper in portraying the image of the ruling and opposition parties of the country. The analysis showed the allying of the said media groups with political parties and how they are working on the agenda of face-saving of one party and face spoiling of the other. In the words of several researchers¹⁶ “the political cartoons in Pakistani newspapers serve as face spoilers for one political party or leader and face saviours for another”. A study¹⁷ examined the semiotic features employed in political cartoons in Jordanian newspapers. This study identified different ideologies and messages in the depiction of cartoons such as democracy, freedom, achievement, victory, and salvation. Their study threw light on the fact that visual communication is an important aspect of political discourse that gives us the insight to decipher the implicit meanings of a discourse. A researcher examined¹⁴ how meaning is interpreted that is embedded in the ads of political campaigns. In his study, he analyzed the political adverts of a popular Nigerian leader, Dr. Goodluck Jonathan. He argued that even though the employment of semiotic resources in political adverts does not impart accurate or true information, they captivate the audience, and this results in the enlargement of the fan following of the leaders which is the main purpose of the advert.

Background of the Study

Pakistan Tehreek I Insaf and Muslim League N are two major political parties in Pakistan. Each of these parties after forming its government at the provincial and national levels initiated some welfare programs for the public. Among many of these programs, one is the initiative of a health program. In the year 2015, the PTI government in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa launched this public health program and distributed cards to deserving ones (Incpak.com). PML-N during their government in 2016 started a health program to facilitate

the people to get free medical treatment (The Nation). For this purpose, the government issued cards to eligible and needy people. As of now, the federal PTI government in Federal relaunched this health insurance program and distributed health cards to eligible people. The Prime Minister's health card by the PML-N govt in 2016 and the national health card issued by the PTI government in 2021 will be our focus of analysis in this study. The study has the following main objectives:

- To do a comparative analysis of the semiotic and linguistic features of the health card.
- To analyze how political ideologies are depicted in the cards.

The objectives are achieved by addressing the following questions:

- What type of semiotic and linguistic features are employed in the health cards?
- How the political ideologies of both parties are depicted in the cards?

Methodology

The data for this study is obtained from the following two links. From the first link, the image of the health card during the PML-N's government is downloaded; <https://www.pakistantimes.com/topics/wp-content/uploads/2015/12/Pakistan-national-health-program.jpg>. Second is the link from where we got the image of the health card issued by the PTI led government: <https://i.ytimg.com/vi/O8TaPXbaof0/maxresdefault.jpg>. In this paper, the researcher aims to analyze the text and image of the cards. The semiotic features will be interpreted and Urdu text on the card will be subject to linguistic analysis after transcribing and translating into the English language. The researcher has used a qualitative descriptive approach to analyze the data. A qualitative and descriptive approach is generally adopted for analysis. In a descriptive analysis, the researchers first collect the data, apply some existing theory, and then come to the ultimate theoretical conclusions of the findings.¹⁸ According to Kriyantono, "Qualitative research aims to explain phenomena in depth through in-depth data collection."

Theoretical Framework

For the present study, we chose the theoretical model proposed by Kress and Van Leeuwen¹⁹ for visual analysis, and the interpretation of the text written on the cards, we will take insight from Norman Fairclough's three-dimensional model for textual analysis. Images

and visuals are important aspects of a discourse that need separate consideration. According to Kress and Leeuwen, “To function as a full system of communication, the visual, like all semiotic modes, has to serve several representational and communicational requirements”. According to this framework, there are three types of functions of images; representational function, interactive function, and compositional function.²⁰

Representational Function

It refers to the ways the image represents the world as it is experienced by people. Kress and Leeuwen suggest that representation is of two types; narrative and conceptual. The narrative representation includes Participants and vectors. Participants refer to people, places, and things that are present in the image. Vectors are oblique lines such as arrows or tools. Conceptual Representations are Analytical and symbolic processes.²¹

Interactive Function

It refers to the relation of the viewer with the vectors and participants presented in the image. The first element is interaction. It includes the gaze, size of the frame, and horizontal and vertical angles. Gaze denotes the eye contact between the viewer and the participant of the image. The frame size hints at the social distance. Vertical angles show the differences in power owned by the participants in the image.

Compositional Function

It refers to the organization and patterning of the elements in the image that influence the overall message of the image. The composition has three types of interconnected systems. The first is known as information value. It refers to the placement of components in the image in a manner that shows their specific values and information. Second, salience is the feature that refers to the organization of elements in the picture that bring into focus the key aspect of the image. The third is framing and it is linked with the absence or presence of an outline around the picture.²²

Fairclough’s Three-Dimensional Model

Fairclough proposed an analytical framework to analyze discourse which is three-dimensional. The first dimension of this model conducts textual analysis in terms of spoken or written text and is titled a description. The Discourse as text dimension deals with “the linguistic features and organization of concrete instances of discourse.”²³ It deals with the speaker’s choice of words such as transitivity and modality, metaphors, similes, cohesive

devices, turn-taking, and other textual structures.²⁴ The second-dimension views language as discursive practices (“processes of text production, distribution and consumption”) and the third dimension analyzes discursive events as socio-cultural practice.²⁵ It is a framework that allows analyzing a text at micro, macro, and meso levels. Micro-level analysis interprets the textual or linguistic features of discourse and macro-level helps to bring forth the ideologies embedded in the text structure.²⁶ It is the framework that is to be used in the current paper. In the present study, we use the Fairclough three-dimensional model, the reason for using this approach is that it gives us a detailed framework for working within CDA. Fairclough justifies it as, “to fully understand what discourse is and how it works, analysis needs to draw out the form and function of the text, the way that this text relates to the way it is produced and consumed, and the relation of this to the wider society in ¹which it takes place.”²⁷

Analysis and Discussion

The analysis of the cards showed that visual elements are not something randomly depicted rather they construct and exhibit various social, national, and political ideologies. The following section will have a detailed analysis of the cards in which visual and textual interpretation is intermingled to decipher meanings in the images.

PML-N Health Card

In this card, different semiotic features can be found. The picture has images of different people but there is one image that seems the most prominent. It is the picture of the then Prime Minister of Pakistan and the president of a major political party Muslim League Noon, Muhammad Nawaz Sharif. The projection of his picture can be interpreted from various points of view. First, it indicates that the Health Program was launched when PML-N was in rule in Pakistan. So, from the political perspective, it adds to the credit of this party which initiated a public welfare program. It depicts PML-N as the political party that is aware of the economic and financial conditions of its middle-class people, so this program will be facilitative to those in need. It constructs the positive image of this political party. Thirdly, being the Prime Minister of Pakistan, his image shows that he is the representative of the whole nation, therefore, the health program is advantageous for every citizen of this country without any discrimination. It integrated political and national ideologies.

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The size of the image of the Prime Minister is bigger than the other participants in the picture. It constitutes the power hierarchy showing that one is more powerful than the others one is ruling, and the others are its subordinates. The image is closely taken from the front and with a slight side pose. There are two contact strategies underlined in this image to develop a direct reader/viewer or addresser/addressee relationship. First, the shot is taken from the front, although a slight side pose can be observed yet it succeeded in developing an engaging social relationship with its onlookers or viewers. It makes the viewer feel that the participant is directly involved with him. Secondly, the image shows that the participant is friendly as he wears a smile on his face and a direct gaze of his eyes helps maintain eye contact with the viewer. In the minds of people, it creates an engaging and friendly impression of the PM.

The fact that PM has initiated the health program for its public is enhanced by the text written on the card near the red crescent. The text is an English tagline written in Urdu transcript. The text can be transcribed as **Prime Minister National Health Program**. The use of the word “Prime Minister” shows that he is one on whose name the program is named. “National” hints that it is not limited to any one province or region rather it is for the whole country.

The angle of the image adds to the compositional meaning. The image of PM is placed on the right side and it is emerging from behind the crescent and is placed between the

crescent and the star. This image covers almost one-third part of the total picture which adds to the foregrounding of the image. The card has a dominant green colour that has some semiotic meanings. The green colour that is employed here in this picture is not equal. On the right side of the card, the colour is thickened and darkened and on the left side, it is lighter and gives a yellowish touch. This not only adds to the appeal of the card but also depicts a political ideology. The national flag of Pakistan has a white and green colour with a crescent and star. The party flag of PML-N is also in green colour with a white star and crescent in the middle of the flag. The protrusion of green colour in the card of a national program shows more of a political promotion of a certain party than a national ideology.

The picture has some icons as well. There is a red crescent from behind there emerges the black and white images of a few people. The red crescent is a historical allusion and it stands for emergency assistance to sick and wounded people. The white and black image of the people shows a representation of the people who can benefit from this health program. There is an image of an elderly woman, two men, a boy, and a girl. They are collectively shown behind the red crescent over the map of Pakistan, waving the national flag of Pakistan over the heads of people. It shows that every deserving citizen of Pakistan can get the benefits of this health program and there is no discrimination. The image of the people is taken from a long distance and we hardly observe their faces that are drawn into white and black. All of the participants in the image have a smile on their face and they are directly looking at the viewers. However, they are depicted in the background with less focus on them. The small size of the image shows that they are less powerful.

There is another tagline that needs interpretation. It is an Urdu line that can be transcribed in English as "Treatment: your right, our responsibility". Here the pronouns 'you' and 'our' develop a direct relationship between the addresser and addressee. The addresser here is the government of Pakistan which presented itself as responsible for providing the facility of treatment and the addressee is the people of Pakistan for whom this program has been initiated. The tagline denotes that the health and well-being of the nation is the responsibility of the state.

PTI Health Card

The health card of PTI led government has striking similarities and differences with the previous government's card. Every political party has its political flag with particular colours

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and icons. This political element is even more apparent in the design and texture of the card that is part of a national interest program. The PTI government also projected the colours of its flag into the health card. The flag of PTI has red and green colours that are equally distributed in the flag. The flag has two parts; one half is green with a white-colored crescent and star, and the second half is all red. The health care card has the colours of PTI's flag. It shows the amalgamation of a certain political party's ideology with national ideology. It indicates that political parties have a general behaviour to depict their own identity in national programs. In this sense, this card is similar to the previous card as both of the cards have the colours of the flags of the said parties. However, PTI's card is different from PML-N's as it does not have the image of its leader in the picture.

The logo of the federal government is printed under a layer of red and green colors which shows that it is a national program and the federal government is undertaking it. In the upper corner of the right-hand side, there is an icon and some text written beneath it. This is an icon of a healthy family. It represents a man, a woman, and two children in the protection of two hands. It implicitly gives the meaning that the government is aware of the fact that health is an important concern of our people and family is the basic unit of society, therefore, it took the initiative to launch this health program. The whole nation is a beneficiary of this program.

Besides semiotic features, there are also some linguistic elements. The text is written in Urdu, the national language of Pakistan. It shows the solidarity and the construction of

national ideology. Under the family icon, there is given the title of the health program by the PTI government. It is termed a “sehat sahulat program” which can be translated as a **Health Insurance Program**. unlike PML-N’s title, it does not include the word Prime Minister’s program. there are two other phrases as well written on the top-middle of the card. The one is the title of the card, **Sehat Insaf Card**. Sehat refers to health and the word ‘Insaf’ needs some interpretation. The word ‘insaf’ is taken from the name of the party, Pakistan Tehreek I Insaf. The word ‘insaf’ creates a reference to the political identity of the PTI’s party and it clearly shows that this initiative has been taken by the PTI’s government. It earns the party the credit of this program and makes it popular or acceptable to the people. The second phrase observes a repetition of the word ‘insaf’ as in “Sehat insaf ky sath” translated as **Health with Insaf**. It hints at the political promotion of one’s party instead of making it a matter of national ideology.

Comparatively, in this card, there is no use of any kind of pronouns whereas in the previous card, there a direct addresser/addressee relationship is established between the writer and the reader. There is no projection of any kind of human pictures in this card, so it gives it an impersonal touch.

Conclusion

The present paper analyzed the semiotic and linguistic features of the health cards that were issued by the government of PML-N in 2016 and the government of PTI in 2021. The features of the cards were analyzed comparatively to show how each of the cards is similar or different from each other and how both political parties construct their political ideologies by employing different techniques such as colors, images, or text. The study tried to explain the meanings of semiotic elements and linguistic expressions to bring forth what is being communicated to the reader and in what manner. The findings of the study revealed that each of the political parties incorporated their political ideologies in the card and intermingled it with the national ideology. The study provides futuristic insight to the researchers who are interested in finding out the incorporation of political ideologies through semiotic and visual elements embedded in the discourse.

References

- ¹ Barry, David, Brigid Carroll, and Hans Hsansen. "To text or context? Endotextual, exotextual, and multi-textual approaches to narrative and discursive organizational studies." *Organization Studies* 27, no. 8 (2006): 1091-1110.
- ² Blommaert, Jan, and Chris Bulcaen. "Critical discourse analysis." *Annual review of Anthropology* 29, no. 1 (2000): 447-466.
- ³ Fairclough, Norman. "Critical discourse analysis." In *The Routledge handbook of discourse analysis*, pp. 9-20. Routledge, 2013.
- ⁴ Bezemer, Jeff, and Diane Mavers. "Multimodal transcription as academic practice: A social semiotic perspective." *International Journal of Social Research Methodology* 14, no. 3 (2011): 191-206.
- ⁵ Kress, Gunther, and Theo Van Leeuwen. *Reading images: The grammar of visual design*. Routledge, 2020.
- ⁶ Napitupulu, Lilis Handayani, Evi Novalin Bako, Nining Rahayu Ars, and Thyrhaya Zein. "A multimodal analysis of advertisement of online marketplace Shopee." *KnE Social Sciences* (2018): 452-460.
- ⁷ Al-Momani, Kawakib, Muhammad A. Badarneh, and Fathi Migdadi. "A semiotic analysis of political cartoons in Jordan in light of the Arab Spring." *Humor* 30, no. 1 (2017): 63-95
- ⁸ Ademilokun, Mohammed, and Moji Olateju. "A multimodal discourse analysis of some visual images in the political rally discourse of 2011 electioneering campaigns in Southwestern Nigeria." *International Journal of Society, Culture & Language* 4, no. 1 (Special Issue on African cultures and Languages) (2016): 1-19.9
- ¹⁰ Ademilokun, Mohammed, and Moji Olateju. "A multimodal discourse analysis of some visual images in the political rally discourse of 2011 electioneering campaigns in Southwestern Nigeria." *International Journal of Society, Culture & Language* 4, no. 1 (Special Issue on African cultures and Languages) (2016): 1-19.9
- ¹¹ Fairclough, Norman. "Critical discourse analysis." In *The Routledge handbook of discourse analysis*, pp. 9-20. Routledge, 2013.
- ¹² Kress, Gunther. "Reading images: Multimodality, representation and new media." *Information Design Journal* 12, no. 2 (2004): 110-119.
- ¹³ Stoian, Claudia Elena. "Analysing images." *Buletinul Stiintific al Universitatii Politehnica din Timisoara, Seria Limbi Moderne* 14 (2015): 23-31.
- ¹⁴ Rymes, Betsy, Mariana Souto-Manning, and Cati Brown. "Being 'critical' as taking a stand: One of the central dilemmas of cda." (2005).
- ¹⁵ Bacchi, Carol. "Policy as discourse: What does it mean? Where does it get us?." *Discourse: studies in the cultural politics of education* 21, no. 1 (2000): 45-57.
- ¹⁶ Chimombo, Moira, and Robert L. Roseberry. *The power of discourse: An introduction to discourse analysis*. Routledge, 2013

- ¹⁷ Maingueneau, Dominique, and John P. O'regan. "Is discourse analysis critical? and This risky order of discourse." *Critical Discourse Studies* 3, no. 2 (2006): 229-235.
- ¹⁸ 19Anderson, Kate T., and Jessica Holloway. "Discourse analysis as theory, method, and epistemology in studies of education policy." *Journal of Education Policy* 35, no. 2 (2020): 188-221.
- ¹⁹ Pedersen, Ove K. "Discourse analysis." (2009).
- ²⁰ 15Bacchi, Carol. "Policy as discourse: What does it mean? Where does it get us?" *Discourse: studies in the cultural politics of education* 21, no. 1 (2000): 45-57
- ²¹ Rogers, Rebecca. "A critical discourse analysis of the special education referral process: A case study." *Discourse: studies in the cultural politics of education* 24, no. 2 (2003): 139-158.
- ²² Bhatia, Vijay K., John Flowerdew, and Rodney H. Jones. "Approaches to discourse analysis." In *Advances in discourse studies*, pp. 11-28. Routledge, 2008.
- ²³ Woodside-Jiron, Haley. "Language, power, and participation: Using critical discourse analysis to make sense of public policy." In *An introduction to critical discourse analysis in education*, pp. 203-236. Routledge, 2004.
- ²⁴ Willett, Rebekah. "Making, makers, and makerspaces: A discourse analysis of professional journal articles and blog posts about makerspaces in public libraries." *The library quarterly* 86, no. 3 (2016): 313-329.
- ²⁵ Rehman, Khalil Ur, Farooq Ahmed, Khurram Shahzad, Muhammad Azam, Saba Iram, and Shahzada Shoaib Ahmed. "Persuasion and Political Discourse: A Critical Discourse Analysis of Imran Khan's Unga Speech (74TH Session: 2019)." *PalArch's Journal of Archaeology of Egypt/Egyptology* 18, no. 09 (2021): 1421-1434
- ²⁶ Jakhar, Altaf Ali, Faheemudin Shaikh, and Farooq Ahmed. "Comparison between spoken and written discourse and its implication in teaching English as second/foreign language." *Agathos* 11, no. 1 (2020): 163-175.
- ²⁷ Ahmed, Farooq, Sehrish Shafi, Nabeela Khalid, and Ramisa Arif. "Critical Discourse Analysis of PM Imran Khan and Shahbaz Sharif's Speeches at UNGA." *International Journal of Social Science Archives (IJSSA)* 6, no. 3 (2023): 86-95.